

Single top quark production at the LHC

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Abstract

This proceeding contains single top quark production measurements based on 8 and 13 TeV datasets collected by the ATLAS and CMS experiments at the LHC. In the t -channel, the fiducial and the inclusive production cross sections of the top quark and top antiquark, the total cross section, and the ratio of top quark and top antiquark cross sections. In addition, the measurements of the differential cross sections are presented. Measurements of the inclusive and the differential production cross sections of a single top quark in association with a W boson are included, as well as the first measurement of the quantum interference between tW and top quark and top antiquark pairs. The first evidence of the single top quark production in association with a Z boson or with a photon is presented.

1 Introduction

The top quark is interesting in many aspects, it is the heaviest elementary particle known and many theories that try to extend the Standard Model (SM) predict particles that are strongly coupled to it. Unlike other quarks it decays before hadronising, which allows the study of the properties of a free quark. According to the SM, the top quark can be produced singly via weak interactions, and at leading order (LO) through three production modes: t -channel with the highest production rate, Wt with the second largest production cross section, and then s -channel which has the smallest production rate and is very challenging at the LHC. Finally, the SM predicts electroweak production of rare processes such as the single top quark in association with a Z boson (tZq), or in association with a photon ($tq\gamma$), which have not been observed yet. The tZq in

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particular is an interesting process since it is sensitive to the tZ and WWZ couplings. In addition it is a background for many searches such as the production of tZ through Flavour Changing Neutral Current (FCNC) processes.

Single top quark production allows validating the SM. In particular, the production cross section is proportional to the V_{tb} CKM matrix element, therefore it tests the unitarity of the CKM matrix; in addition, it helps constraining Parton distribution functions (PDF) and tuning Monte Carlo (MC) event generators.

2 t -channel cross section measurements

The production of the top quark through the t -channel occurs when a light quark from one of the colliding protons interacts with a b -quark from the other proton by exchanging a virtual W boson. Single top quark production through the t -channel is studied by ATLAS experiment [?] using 20.2 fb^{-1} of integrated luminosity at $\sqrt{s} = 8 \text{ TeV}$ [?]. Events are required to have exactly one reconstructed well isolated lepton with high transverse momentum. In addition, events are required to have exactly two jets with high p_T , in which exactly one jet is required to be b -tagged by an algorithm optimised to reject c quark jets to reduce the major background, Wc production. The remaining jet is an untagged and is typically produced at large η . To enhance the signal background ratio (S/B), two Bayesian neural networks are trained for the top quark and for the top antiquark channels separately, where the variable making the most significant contribution is the invariant mass of the system consisting of untagged jet and b -tagged jet $m(jb)$.

To minimise the MC generator systematic uncertainties, fiducial cross sections are measured first using binned likelihood fits performed on the full NN distributions separately. Where the fiducial volume is defined using stable particles selected by cuts very close to those applied in the event selection. The fiducial cross sections are extrapolated to the full phase space to measure the inclusive and these are compared to predictions made by different MC generators. The ratio between the top quark and top antiquark production cross sections is measured to be $R_t = 1.7 \pm 0.09$ and compared with predictions made by different proton PDFs. The sum of the full cross sections of the top quark and top antiquark is used to extract the CKM $|V_{tb}|$ element without assuming of unitarity on the CKM matrix, and the result is $|V_{tb}| = 1.029 \pm 0.048$.

The top quark and the top antiquark cross sections are measured as a function of p_T and absolute rapidity ($|y|$) at both the parton and particle levels. The p_T and $|y|$ differential cross sections of the untagged jet are also measured but only at the particle level. The differential distributions are measured from a signal enriched sample by selecting events with high NN score. These distributions are unfolded and directly compared to predictions made by different MC generators.

Figure 1: Left) measured R_t by ATLAS at $\sqrt{s} = 8$ TeV [?], and right) CMS measured R_t at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV [?]. Both are compared with predictions made by different PDFs.

Following a similar strategy, the t-channel cross sections are measured by CMS experiment [?] using 35.9 fb^{-1} of integrated luminosity at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV [?]. The same event signature, and different events categories are defined according to the number of jets and b -tagged jets. Two BDTs are trained to enhance the S/B but trained in $2j1b$ region for the electron and muon channels separately. The two BDTs are applied to the $2j1b$, $3j1b$, and $3j2b$ categories, separately for the two different flavours and charges of the lepton. Finally, 12 regions are used in the final binned likelihood fit to extract the total production cross section for top quark and top antiquark. The extracted value of R_t is 1.65 ± 0.02 (stat.) ± 0.04 (syst.), while the extracted of the $|V_{tb}|$ CKM element is $|V_{tb}| = 1.00 \pm 0.005$ (stat.) ± 0.02 (theo.). Figure ?? shows the measured cross section ratio of the top quark and top antiquarks compared to predictions made using different proton PDF sets.

3 Wt channel cross section measurements

The total production cross section of the Wt process in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 8$ TeV is measured using 20.3 fb^{-1} and 12.2 fb^{-1} of integrated luminosity by the ATLAS [?] and CMS [?] collaborations, respectively. The measurements are performed in the dilepton final state where both W bosons decay to an electron or a muon and a neutrino ($e\nu$ or $\mu\nu$). Events are selected by requiring two opposite sign leptons (ee , $e\mu$, $\mu\mu$) with high p_T , high E_T^{miss} and exactly one jet with high p_T , this jet is required to be b -tagged. To constrain backgrounds, control regions enriched with background events are defined using the jets and b -tagged jet multiplicity. Separate Boosted Decision Trees (BDT) are used to enhance the S/B. The cross section is extracted using a profile likelihood fit of the full BDT distributions in the signal and background control regions. The significance of the observed Wt signal is 7.6σ and 5.4σ by ATLAS and CMS, respectively. Both measured cross sections are used to extract the $|V_{tb}|$ CKM

element, leading to $|V_{tb}| = 1.01 \pm 0.10$ by ATLAS and $|V_{tb}| = 1.03 \pm 0.12(\text{exp}) \pm 0.04(\text{th.})$ by CMS.

The Wt production cross section measurement is repeated by CMS using 35.9 fb^{-1} of integrated luminosity collected at $\sqrt{s} = 13 \text{ TeV}$ [?] employing similar techniques as in the 8 TeV measurement. The cross section is extracted using simultaneous binned likelihood of two BDT distributions in $1j1b$ and $2j1b$ regions and p_T distribution of the sub-leading jet. The resulting cross section is $\sigma_{tW} = 63.1 \pm 1.8(\text{stat.}) \pm 6.4(\text{syst.}) \pm 2.1(\text{lumi}) \text{ pb}$.

The differential tW cross section is measured by ATLAS at $\sqrt{s} = 13 \text{ TeV}$. Many kinematic variables are used: $E(b)$, $m(\ell_1b)$, $m(\ell_2b)$, $E(\ell b)$, $m_T(\ell\nu\nu b)$ and $m(\ell b)$. To have a signal enriched sample, events are selected with high BDT score, and to reduce systematic uncertainties, the signal distributions are normalised to the measured fiducial cross section. These differential cross sections are compared to the predictions by some MC generators and found to be in good agreements.

At NLO, the tW process has an identical final state as the $t\bar{t}$ process at LO, resulting in a quantum interference. The tW and the $t\bar{t}$ processes are simulated separately, and this leads to event double counting. To reduce this effect, two schemes are employed by MC generators: diagram removal (DR) and diagram subtractions (DS). The difference between the two schemes is taken as a systematic uncertainty. Traditional measurements of the tW production are designed to be insensitive to such effect, but many searches design analyses that can end in a phase space sensitive to the interference and the systematic effects can be big. Recently, a fixed-order NLO calculation that include a proper treatment of the interference has become available [?]. However, there are no measurements available to assess the modelling. Unlike traditional measurements of the tW production, ATLAS designed an analysis to target the region where the interference effect and the difference between DS/DR is big with the goal of measuring the effect [?]. A variable sensitive to the interference $m_{\ell b}^{\text{minimax}}$ is measured and the unfolded distribution is compared with theoretical models with various implementations of interference effects. It is found that Powheg-Box-Res MC generator models the full $m_{\ell b}^{\text{minimax}}$ well across the full distribution, also beyond the top quark mass where DR/DS diverge.

4 First evidence of the SM tZq production mode

The SM predicts the electroweak production of a single top quark in association with a Z boson (tZq), this process has not been observed. ATLAS [?] and CMS [?] collaborations have searched for tZq at $\sqrt{s} = 13 \text{ TeV}$ using 36.1 fb^{-1} and 35.9 fb^{-1} of integrated luminosity, respectively. The analyses are performed using the trilepton channel, since it the most promising for first observation

despite the small branching fraction.

Events are required to have exactly three leptons, e or μ , well isolated with different p_T cuts to maximise the S/B. The Z boson is reconstructed from a pair of leptons with an opposite sign, same flavour (OSSF). The OSSF pair is required to have an invariant mass within a window from the Z boson mass. The remaining lepton is associated to the W boson that is assumed to come from the top quark decay. In addition, many quality cuts are applied to increase the S/B. ATLAS required events to have exactly two jets while CMS required events to have two or three jets. Exactly one jet is required to be b -tagged and used to reconstruct the top quark, the other jet is called the untagged jet and tends to be in the forward direction as in the t -channel.

ATLAS employed a NN to combine many input variables to enhance the S/B while CMS used BDT, where the variables most effective in separating signal from background are the $|\eta|$ and p_T of the untagged jet.

ATLAS extracted the tZq cross section using a binned maximum likelihood fit that is performed on the full distribution of the NN score of the SR, while CMS extracted the $t\ell\ell q$ cross section using a binned maximum likelihood fit that is performed on the full BDT distributions in the two SR and the m_T distribution of the CR. The ATLAS observed signal significance is 4.2 standard deviation compared to the predicted significance of 5.4, while the CMS observed signal significance is 3.7 standard deviation compared to the predicted significance of 3.1.

5 First evidence of the SM $tq\gamma$ production mode

The CMS collaboration searched for single top quark production in association to a photon $tq\gamma$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV using 35.9 fb^{-1} of integrated luminosity [?]. Events are selected with exactly one high p_T well isolated muon, while events with electrons are not included in the analysis because of the high background. Exactly, one p_T well isolated photon, in addition, two jets in which one is b -tagged. A BDT that combined eight well modelled kinematic variables is used to enhance the S/B, where $\Delta R(\gamma, \text{untagged jet})$ is the most useful variable. The SR plus one CR region are used in the binned likelihood to extract the signal, and the observed significance is 4.4σ while the predicted significance is 3σ .

6 Summary

Both ATLAS and CMS collaborations performed comprehensive analysis of t -channel and W -channel at 8 TeV and 13 TeV. Both experiments have evidence for tZq and the discovery is in the horizon. CMS collaboration has the first evidence for $tq\gamma$. With the full Run2 datasets many precision measurements of

single top quark processes will be possible and single top quark rare production processes can be investigated.

References

- [1] ATLAS Collaboration, *The ATLAS Experiment at the CERN Large Hadron Collider*, *JINST* **3** (2008) S08003.
- [2] CMS Collaboration, *The CMS experiment at the CERN LHC*, *JINST* **3** S08004 (2008).
- [3] ATLAS Collaboration, *Fiducial, total and differential cross-section measurements of t -channel single top-quark production in pp collisions at 8 TeV using data collected by the ATLAS detector*, *Eur. Phys. J.C* **77** (2017) 531, [[hep-ex/1702.02859](#)].
- [4] CMS Collaboration, *Measurement of the single top quark and antiquark production cross sections in the t channel and their ratio in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s}=13$ TeV*, *CMS-PAS-TOP-17-011*.
- [5] ATLAS Collaboration, *Measurement of the inclusive cross-sections of single top-quark and top-antiquark t -channel production in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV with the ATLAS detector*, *JHEP* **1704** (2017) 086 [[hep-ex/1609.03920](#)].
- [6] ATLAS Collaboration, *Measurement of the production cross section of a single top quark in association with a W boson at 8 TeV with the ATLAS experiment*, *JHEP* **1601** (2016) 064, [[hep-ex/1510.03752](#)].
- [7] CMS Collaboration, *Observation of the associated production of a single top quark and a W boson in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 8$ TeV*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **112** (2014) no.23, 231802, [[hep-ex/1401.2942](#)].
- [8] CMS Collaboration, *Measurement of the production cross section for single top quarks in association with W bosons in proton-proton collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV*, *JHEP* **1810** (2018) 117, [[hep-ex/1805.07399](#)].
- [9] ATLAS Collaboration, *Probing the quantum interference between singly and doubly resonant top-quark production in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV with the ATLAS detector*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **121** (2018) no.15, 152002, [[hep-ex/1806.04667](#)].
- [10] F. Cascioli et al., *A unified NLO description of top-pair and associated Wt production*, *Eur. Phys. J. C* **74** (2014) no.3, 2783, [[hep-ph/1312.0546](#) [[hep-ph](#)]].
- [11] ATLAS Collaboration, *Measurement of the production cross-section of a single top quark in association with a Z boson in proton-proton collisions at 13 TeV with the ATLAS detector*, *Phys. Lett. B* **780** (2018) 557, [[hep-ex/1710.03659](#)].

- [12] CMS Collaboration, *Measurement of the associated production of a single top quark and a Z boson in pp collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 7$ TeV*, *Phys. Lett. B* **779** (2018) 358, [[hep-ex/1712.02825](#)].
- [13] CMS Collaboration, *Evidence for the associated production of a single top quark and a photon in proton-proton collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV*, [[hep-ex/arXiv:1808.02913](#)].